

ACADEMIC PROCRASTINATION AMONG STUDENTS: ROLE OF ANXIETY, SOCIO ECONOMIC STATUS AND GENDER

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Abstract

In the modern world, procrastinating is a very prevalent and dangerous problem. Procrastination is defined as a tendency to put off or delay acting or deciding. Academic procrastination appears to be common in academic environments, since students frequently put off completing assignments until the very last minute, usually without good reason. The current investigation was done to inspect the academic procrastination among students with respect to their anxiety, socio-economic status (SES) and gender. Academic procrastination has taken as dependent variable while anxiety (High & Low), SES (Upper class & Lower class) and gender (Male & Female) have taken as independent variables. In the current investigation descriptive survey method was employed. In the present study, multi-stage random sampling technique was used to select the sample of 600 senior secondary school students studying in senior secondary schools, affiliated to Central Board of School Education (CBSE) of Rohtak and Jhajjar Districts of Haryana State. Academic Procrastination Scale Developed by the Investigator herself. Anxiety Scale by Sarkar and Das (2020) and Socio-economic Status (SESS-BR) by Bharadwaj (2014) were apply to gather the data. "The obtained data was analyzed using Three Way ANOVA with $2 \times 2 \times 2$ factorial design. Result of the study revealed that the interaction effect of anxiety, socio-economic status (SES) and gender on academic procrastination of sr. sec. school students was found to be significant".

Keywords: "Academic Procrastination, Anxiety, Gender, Socio-economic Status"

INTRODUCTION

In the modern world, procrastinating is a very prevalent and dangerous problem. The usual definition of procrastination is the tendency to put off or delay acting or deciding. Academic procrastination appears to be common in academic environments, since students frequently put off completing assignments until the very last minute, usually without good reason.

According to research, between 30 to 40 percent of students believe that procrastination is a serious issue that impairs their ability to balance their personal and professional lives. This is especially true for elementary school students who put off completing many assignments until the last minute, which increases stress levels and may have a detrimental impact on their academic performance. Primary academic responsibilities including lesson planning, term paper and test revision, and other academic issues and activities related to education are put off. Thus, postponing academic assignments and the problems that result from doing so are considered academic procrastination. The problem of procrastination is much more serious than it seems to be. It is prevalent in all corners of the world. Students in schools and colleges face a face a very common problem about procrastination in academic field. Some others avoid for a longer time or ever forever. Even some students think that procrastination can lead them to mental stress, so they do less procrastination. Over all the performance depends positively on the lower degree of procrastination (Solomon & Rothblum, 1984).

Academic procrastination is defined as waiting until the last minute to begin or finish an assignment that is due. Approximately 80% to 95% of school students struggle with academic procrastination, according to research done as early as 1979 and 2000 by Ellis and Knaus. Academic procrastination hurts performance because it is associated with negative behaviours like bad study habits, cramming for exams, test anxiety, turning in homework assignments and term papers late, receiving lower grades, and experiencing feelings of guilt and depression (Klassen, 2008). While most students turn in their projects by the deadline, some students give in their work after the deadline or never turn it in at all (Owens and Newbegin, 2000). Although there are a variety of reasons why the work was not turned in on time, the most common ones are illegitimate or implausible (Schubert, 2000).

Anxiety is an unpleasant internal state which involves the anticipation of a threatening situation that may occur in the future. It is different from fear, which occurs in response to a real or definite threat. Anxiety is associated with both avoidant behaviour and cautious or vigilant behaviour in preparation for the anticipated threat (American Psychiatric Association, 2013). In the Indian context, academic procrastination is significantly linked to anxiety among students. High levels of anxiety often lead to increased procrastination behaviors due to fear of failure or overwhelming tasks, which in turn can exacerbate anxiety levels further creating a cyclical pattern. Kaur (2023) showed positive relationship between academic procrastination and anxiety of senior secondary school students. Anxiety is a multifaceted experience that encompasses worry, emotional instability, fear of failure, low

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self-esteem, and lack of confidence and peace of mind (World Health Organization, 2024; Fernandes, 2022). Anxiety among students may arise from factors such as last-minute studying, sleep deprivation, and poor time management. These stressors can lead to behaviors like mugging up for exams, fear of forgetting information, inadequate effort, guilt, and poor academic performance affecting class engagement (Desai, et.al., 2021). Furthermore, students tend to procrastinate on work as a result of anxiety. Beyond learning, anxiety influences social interactions and physical and mental health (Moonaghi and Beydokhti, 2017).

SES is defined as a measure of individuals' combined economic and social status, which may influence many aspects of personal behaviors. In addition, lower SES affects the procrastination tendency of students, as students with lower SES are more worried about their financial situation, which triggers anxiety and leads to increased academic procrastination (Stöber and Joormann, 2001). Similarly, differences in SES can also explain to certain extent the tendency of individuals to use Facebook to avoid or procrastinate on tasks (Arnett, 2016). Furthermore, a recent study measured childhood SES and investigated its relationship with procrastination found that SES is closely related to procrastination via parenting style and conscientiousness trait (Shimamura et al., 2021). Such associations could be attributed to the personality-trait formation. Yao (2020) reported a significant negative correlation between SES and procrastination. Milgram et al. (1995) conducted a study investigating the relationship between procrastination and related variables among 115 male and 85 female students, concluding that males were more likely to procrastinate than females. Lu, et.al. (2021) found that the general tendency and academic procrastination tendency of males were stronger than females. Understanding the consequences of procrastination is crucial, particularly in the field of academics. However, there is a lack of literature focusing on procrastination issues that could be a marker of anxiety disorder. Hence, we conducted this study to analyze the role of anxiety, socio-economic status and gender in prevalence of academic procrastination among students.

OBJECTIVE: “To study the interaction effect of Anxiety, Socio Economic Status and Gender on Academic Procrastination among senior secondary school students.”

HYPOTHESIS: “There is no significant interaction effect of Anxiety, Socio Economic Status and Gender on Academic Procrastination among senior secondary school students.”

DESIGN AND METHODOLOGY

“In the present study, descriptive survey method was used. The $2 \times 2 \times 2$ factorial randomized group design was used to analyze the data. All the independent variables i.e. Anxiety (High & Low), Socio-economic status (Upper class & Lower class) and Gender (Male & Female) were varied at the two levels as given below”.

SAMPLE

In the present study, multi-stage random sampling technique was used to select the sample of 600 senior secondary school students studying in senior secondary schools, affiliated to Central Board of School Education (CBSE) of Rohtak and Jhajjar Districts of Haryana State. Out of 22 districts of Haryana two districts were chosen randomly by employing lottery method (making slips of districts and putting them into a handmade card board box). Two districts namely Rohtak & Jhajjar were chosen respectively.

TOOLS USED

- **Academic Procrastination Scale** Developed by the Investigator herself.
- **Anxiety Scale** by Sarkar and Das (2020).
- **Socio-economic Status (SESS-BR)** by Bharadwaj (2014).

STATISTICAL TECHNIQUES

“The Three-Way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) with $2 \times 2 \times 2$ Factorial Design was computed using SPSS 20 version to study the interaction effects of the independent variables i.e. Anxiety, Socio-economic status and Gender on academic procrastination among senior secondary school students. Wherever F-value was found significant, ‘t’-test was employed for further investigation”.

DATA ANALYSIS & INTERPRETATION

“For examine the interaction effect of anxiety, socio-economic status and gender on academic procrastination, data were subjected to analysis of variance (ANOVA) of a $(2 \times 2 \times 2)$ factorial

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study with a randomized group design. Anxiety (A), Socio-economic Status (B) and Gender (C) were coded as A, B, C respectively & were diverse into two ways as: High (A1) & Low (A2); Upper Class (B1) & Lower Class (B2); Male (C1) & Female (C2). The summary of ANOVA (2×2×2) has also been presented in Table-1, which is analyzed in terms of interaction effects”.

Table-1

“Summary of Three Way ANOVA (2x2x2 Factorial Design) for Academic Procrastination of Senior Secondary School Students with respect to Anxiety, Socio-economic Status and Gender”

DV: Academic Procrastination	Df	Sum of Squares (SS)	Mean Squares (MSS)	F-ratio
Interaction Effect				
A×B×C Interaction	1	12678.997	12678.997	10.610**
Between Cells	7	66526.592
Within Cells	392	486206.345	1240.322	
Total	399			

*** Significant at 0.01 level * Significant at 0.05 level NS= Not Significant”

“The Table-1 indicates that the F- ratio (10.610) for the interaction effect of anxiety x SES x gender on academic procrastination of senior secondary school students is found significant at 0.01 level. Therefore, the null hypothesis H_{010} “There is no significant triple interaction effect of anxiety, socio-economic status and gender on academic procrastination among senior secondary school students” stands rejected. Further, t- test was employed to find out the difference in mean scores of academic procrastination among senior secondary school students for different groups. The results for the same have been presented in the Table-2.

Table-2

t-values for Mean Scores of Academic Procrastination among Senior secondary school students for Different Groups of Anxiety, Socio-economic Status (SES) and Gender (AxBxC)

Sr. No.	Group	N		Means		S.D.s		t-values
1	A ₁ B ₁ C ₁ vs A ₁ B ₁ C ₂	45	38	56.33	72.55	27.41	36.64	2.24*
2	A ₂ B ₂ C ₁ vs A ₂ B ₂ C ₂	35	43	63.54	102.32	36.74	40.74	4.41**
3	A ₁ B ₁ C ₁ vs A ₁ B ₂ C ₂	45	60	56.33	83.79	27.41	38.37	4.27**
4	A ₁ B ₁ C ₂ vs A ₁ B ₂ C ₂	38	60	72.55	83.79	36.64	38.37	1.45 (NS)
5	A ₁ B ₂ C ₁ vs A ₂ B ₁ C ₂	56	59	69.85	84.18	31.43	36.79	2.24*
6	A ₁ B ₂ C ₂ vs A ₂ B ₂ C ₂	60	43	83.79	102.32	38.37	40.74	2.33*
7	A ₁ B ₁ C ₁ vs A ₂ B ₂ C ₂	45	43	56.33	102.32	27.41	40.74	6.18**
8	A ₁ B ₁ C ₂ vs A ₁ B ₂ C ₁	38	56	72.55	69.85	36.64	31.43	0.371 (NS)
9	A ₂ B ₁ C ₁ vs A ₂ B ₂ C ₁	64	35	85.40	63.54	32.98	36.74	2.93**
10	A ₁ B ₁ C ₁ vs A ₂ B ₁ C ₁	45	64	56.33	85.40	27.41	32.98	5.01**
11	A ₁ B ₁ C ₂ vs A ₂ B ₁ C ₂	38	59	72.55	84.18	36.64	36.79	1.52 (NS)
12	A ₁ B ₂ C ₂ vs A ₂ B ₂ C ₁	60	35	83.79	63.54	38.37	36.74	2.25*
13	A ₁ B ₁ C ₂ vs A ₂ B ₂ C ₂	38	43	72.55	102.32	36.64	40.74	3.46**
14	A ₁ B ₂ C ₁ vs A ₁ B ₂ C ₂	56	60	69.85	83.79	31.43	38.37	2.14*
15	A ₁ B ₁ C ₁ vs A ₂ B ₁ C ₂	45	59	56.33	84.18	27.41	36.79	4.42**
16	A ₁ B ₂ C ₁ vs A ₂ B ₂ C ₁	56	35	69.85	63.54	31.43	36.74	0.842 (NS)
17	A ₁ B ₁ C ₂ vs A ₂ B ₁ C ₁	38	64	72.55	85.40	36.64	32.98	1.77(NS)
18	A ₁ B ₂ C ₁ vs A ₂ B ₂ C ₂	56	43	69.85	102.32	31.43	40.74	4.32**
19	A ₁ B ₂ C ₂ vs A ₂ B ₁ C ₁	60	64	83.79	85.40	38.37	32.98	0.249 (NS)
20	A ₁ B ₁ C ₁ vs A ₂ B ₂ C ₁	45	35	56.33	63.54	27.41	36.74	0.970 (NS)
21	A ₁ B ₂ C ₁ vs A ₂ B ₁ C ₁	56	64	69.85	85.40	31.43	32.98	2.64*
22	A ₁ B ₂ C ₂ vs A ₂ B ₁ C ₂	60	59	83.79	84.18	38.37	36.79	0.056 (NS)
23	A ₂ B ₁ C ₁ vs A ₂ B ₁ C ₂	64	59	85.40	84.18	32.98	36.79	0.193 (NS)
24	A ₁ B ₁ C ₂ vs A ₂ B ₂ C ₁	38	35	72.55	63.54	36.64	36.74	1.04 (NS)
25	A ₂ B ₁ C ₁ vs A ₂ B ₂ C ₂	64	43	85.40	102.32	32.98	40.74	2.26*
26	A ₂ B ₁ C ₂ vs A ₂ B ₂ C ₁	59	35	84.18	63.54	36.79	36.74	2.63*
27	A ₂ B ₁ C ₂ vs A ₂ B ₂ C ₂	59	43	84.18	102.32	36.79	40.74	2.31*
28	A ₁ B ₁ C ₁ vs A ₁ B ₂ C ₁	45	56	56.33	69.85	27.41	31.43	2.30*

** Significant at 0.01 level * Significant at 0.05 level NS = Not Significant

Table-2 indicates that t-values 1.45, 0.371, 1.52, 0.842, 1.77, 0.249, 0.970, 0.056, 0.193 and 1.04 for the groups $A_1B_1C_2$ vs $A_1B_2C_2$; $A_1B_1C_2$ vs $A_1B_2C_1$; $A_1B_1C_2$ vs $A_2B_1C_2$; $A_1B_2C_1$ vs $A_2B_2C_1$; $A_1B_1C_2$ vs $A_2B_1C_1$; $A_1B_2C_2$ vs $A_2B_1C_1$; $A_1B_1C_1$ vs $A_2B_2C_1$; $A_1B_2C_2$ vs $A_2B_1C_2$; $A_2B_1C_1$ vs $A_2B_1C_2$ and $A_1B_1C_2$ vs $A_2B_2C_1$ respectively are not found significant at 0.05 level leading to the inference that students of these groups did not differ significantly.

An examination of Table-2 reveals that t-value (2.24) for male students having high anxiety with upper class socio-economic status ($A_1B_1C_1$) and female students having high anxiety with upper class socio-economic status ($A_1B_1C_2$) is found significant at 0.05 level. Mean scores highlighted that male students having high anxiety with upper class socio-economic status (56.33) have less academic procrastination than female students having high anxiety with upper class socio-economic status ($A_1B_1C_2$). The t-value (4.41) for male students having low anxiety with lower class socio-economic status ($A_2B_2C_1$) and female students having low anxiety with lower class socio-economic status ($A_2B_2C_2$) is found significant at 0.01 level. Average scores represented that male students having low anxiety with lower class socio-economic status (63.54) exhibit less academic procrastination than female students having low anxiety with lower class socio-economic status (102.32). It is evident from table-2 that the t-value (4.27) for male students having high anxiety with upper class socio-economic status ($A_1B_1C_1$) and male students having low anxiety with lower class socio-economic status ($A_1B_2C_2$) is found significant at 0.01 level. In terms of mean scores, it can be concluded that male students having high anxiety with upper class socio-economic status (56.33) have less academic procrastination as compared to male students having low anxiety with lower class socio-economic status (83.79).

An examination of table- indicated that t-value (2.24) for male students having high anxiety with lower class socio-economic status ($A_1B_2C_1$) and female students having high anxiety with upper class socio-economic status ($A_2B_1C_2$) is found significant at 0.05 level. Average scores showed that male students having high anxiety with lower class socio-economic status (69.85) possess less academic procrastination than female students having high anxiety with upper class socio-economic status (84.18). The t-value (2.33) for female students having high anxiety with lower class socio-economic status ($A_1B_2C_2$) and female students having low anxiety with lower class socio-economic status ($A_2B_2C_2$) is found significant at 0.05 level. While comparing mean scores, it can be seen that female students having high anxiety with lower class socio-economic status (83.79) have less academic procrastination than female students having low anxiety with lower class socio-economic status (102.32). Similarly, the t-

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value (6.18) for male students having high anxiety with upper class socio-economic status ($A_1B_1C_1$) and female students having low anxiety with lower class socio-economic status ($A_2B_2C_2$) is found significant at 0.01 level. Comparison of mean scores indicated that male students having high anxiety with upper class socio-economic status (56.33) showed less procrastination in academics as compared to female students having low anxiety with lower class socio-economic status (102.32).

It is evident from table-2 that the t-value (2.93) for male students having low anxiety with upper class socio-economic status ($A_2B_1C_1$) and male students having low anxiety with lower class socio-economic status ($A_2B_2C_1$) is found significant at 0.01 level. Average scores highlighted that male students having low anxiety with upper class socio-economic status (85.40) exhibit higher academic procrastination than male students having low anxiety with lower class socio-economic status (63.54). The t-value (5.01) for male students having high anxiety with upper class socio-economic status ($A_1B_1C_1$) and male students having low anxiety with upper class socio-economic status ($A_2B_1C_1$) is found significant at 0.01 level. Mean scores indicated that male students having high anxiety with upper class socio-economic status (56.33) have lesser academic procrastination than male students having low anxiety with upper class socio-economic status (85.40).

An inspection of table-2 showed that the t-value (2.25) for female students having high anxiety with lower class socio-economic status ($A_1B_2C_2$) and male students having low anxiety with lower class socio-economic status ($A_2B_2C_1$) is found significant at 0.05 level. Average scores indicated that female students having high anxiety with lower class socio-economic status (83.79) have higher academic procrastination than male students having low anxiety with lower class socio-economic status (63.54). The t-value (3.46) for female students having high anxiety with upper class socio-economic status ($A_1B_1C_2$) and female students having low anxiety with lower class socio-economic status ($A_2B_2C_2$) is found significant at 0.01 level. Comparison of average scores cleared that female students having high anxiety with upper class socio-economic status (72.55) exhibit less academic procrastination than female students having low anxiety with lower class socio-economic status (102.32). The t-value (2.14) for male students having high anxiety with lower class socio-economic status ($A_1B_2C_1$) and female students having high anxiety with lower class socio-economic status ($A_1B_2C_2$) is found significant at 0.05 level. Mean scores concluded that male students having high anxiety with lower class socio-economic status (69.85) possess

less procrastination in academics than female students having high anxiety with lower class socio-economic status (83.79).

It is palpable from table-2 that the t-value (4.42) for male students having high anxiety with upper class socio-economic status ($A_1B_1C_1$) and female students having low anxiety with upper class socio-economic status ($A_2B_1C_2$) is found significant at 0.01 level. Average scores represented that male students having high anxiety with upper class socio-economic status (56.33) have less academic procrastination as compare to female students having low anxiety with upper class socio-economic status (84.18). The t-value (4.32) for male students having high anxiety with lower class socio-economic status ($A_1B_2C_1$) and female students having low anxiety with lower class socio-economic status ($A_2B_2C_2$) is found significant at 0.01 level. Average scores highlighted that male students having high anxiety with lower class socio-economic status (69.85) exhibit less academic procrastination than female students having low anxiety with lower class socio-economic status (102.32). The t-value (2.64) for male students having high anxiety with lower class socio-economic status ($A_1B_2C_1$) and male students having low anxiety with upper class socio-economic status ($A_2B_1C_1$) is found significant at 0.01 level. Comparison of mean scores indicated that male students having high anxiety with lower class socio-economic status (69.85) possess lower academic procrastination as compared to male students having low anxiety with upper class socio-economic status (85.40).

An examination of Table-2 revealed that the t-value (2.26) for male students having low anxiety with upper class socio-economic status ($A_2B_1C_1$) and female students having low anxiety with lower class socio-economic status ($A_2B_2C_2$) is found significant at 0.05 level. While comparing mean scores, it can be inferred that male students having low anxiety with upper class socio-economic status (85.40) have less academic procrastination than female students having low anxiety with lower class socio-economic status (102.32). The t-value (2.63) for female students having low anxiety with upper class socio-economic status ($A_2B_1C_2$) and male students having low anxiety with lower class socio-economic status ($A_2B_2C_1$) is found significant at 0.01 level. In the context of mean scores, it can be found that female students having low anxiety with upper class socio-economic status (84.18) have higher academic procrastination than male students having low anxiety with lower class socio-economic status (63.54).

Fig. 1: Mean Scores for Interaction Effect of Anxiety, Socio-economic Status and Gender (AxBxC) on Academic Procrastination among senior secondary school students

Table-2 showed that the t-value (2.31) for female students having low anxiety with upper class socio-economic status ($A_2B_1C_2$) and female students having low anxiety with lower class socio-economic status ($A_2B_2C_2$) is found significant at 0.01 level. In terms of mean scores, it can be seen that female students having low anxiety with upper class socio-economic status (84.18) possess lower academic procrastination than female students having low anxiety with lower class socio-economic status (102.32). Lastly, the t-value (2.30) male students having high anxiety with upper class socio-economic status ($A_1B_1C_1$) and male students having high anxiety with lower class socio-economic status ($A_1B_2C_1$) is found significant at 0.05 level. Comparison of average scores, it can be inferred that male students having high anxiety with upper class socio-economic status (56.33) have less academic procrastination as compared to male students having high anxiety with lower class socio-economic status (69.85).

CONCLUSION

Procrastination is a complex, psychologically heterogeneous phenomenon that includes behavioural, emotional and cognitive components. The main areas of manifestation of procrastination are professional and educational activities. Academic procrastination implies a delay in the fulfilment of educational assignments and is associated with undeveloped learning skills, lack of organization, forgetfulness, and behavioural rigidity. The consequence of this behaviour in most cases is the decrease in academic achievement, negative emotional experiences related to own failure, anxiety, and dissatisfaction with the results. Procrastination negatively affects the psychological well-being of students; therefore, this phenomenon is of special interest in the context of future specialists training. Therefore, the government's mandatory role is to provide online, and offline self-motivation and primary-level software databases related to procrastination rectification. Educational administration and teachers will acquaint their pupils about academic procrastination. Value oriented education will be provided to adolescents. Students should spend time talking to parents about their emotional struggles, especially when it comes to academic worries. Students should set up appropriate timelines to avoid living stressful lives by not finishing their work on time. Some programmes related to mind development will be implemented so that adolescents suffer less from anxiety and tension.

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